

Integers are only Primals and Compounds

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Abstract: This study introduces a nuanced framework for classifying integers that transcends the traditional dichotomy of prime and composite numbers. It incorporates: (I) the inclusion of negative integers as primal numbers, (II) the recognition of 1 and -1 as distinct primal numbers, and (III) the classification of 0 as a unique compound number, alongside negative compounds. This approach is rooted in a detailed exploration of prime number sieves across the entire integer spectrum, highlighting the fundamental roles of negative integers, zero, and unity in mathematical constructs. Central to this work is the definition of the complementary pair of divisors and the reconceptualization of integers through their multiplicative relationships, particularly exemplified by the hyperbolic sieve of primes derived from the multiplication table framework. This study argues against the oversimplification inherent in the binary classification of integers into primes and composites based solely on their multiplication or factor properties. Instead, a more comprehensive classification system is proposed, utilizing the concept of divisors to delineate integers with one or two distinct positive divisors as primal numbers, and integers with more than two distinct positive divisors as compound numbers.

Keywords: Sieve of primal numbers, Primal numbers, Compound numbers, Complementary pair of divisors, Negative primes, Zero as a compound number, Fundamental Theorem of Arithmetic, Multiplication table framework.

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*Never believe in a convention about any concept in Number Theory.
Mathematics is like religion. Nobody trusts Divinity by convention.*

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1 Introduction

The concept of prime numbers has historically elicited a sense of perplexity. Throughout history, multiple attempts have been made to elucidate the definition of a prime number, leading to varied and even contradictory interpretations. Even definitions across different languages result in distinct interpretations, influencing the behavior attributed to prime numbers. Historically, attempts to define prime numbers have resulted in varied, evolving definitions, with controversies surrounding the classification of number 1 as prime or not.

Before delving into the diverse historical and linguistic interpretations of prime numbers, let us define two pivotal concepts that underpin this study: 'Primal Numbers' and 'Compound Numbers.' Primal Numbers refer to integers that are traditionally recognized as primes, including the integers 1 and -1, extending the concept to embrace negative primes and the foundational unit of number theory. Compound Numbers, conversely, encompass all non-prime integers, integrating both positive and negative composites along with the number zero, thus offering a holistic view of the integer spectrum.

1.1 Prime Numbers

Prime numbers are integers greater than 1 that have exactly two distinct positive divisors: 1 and themselves. This definition is foundational to number theory, a branch of pure mathematics devoted to the study of the properties and relationships of numbers, especially integers. Prime numbers are considered the building blocks of natural numbers because of the Fundamental Theorem of Arithmetic, which states that every integer greater than 1 can be uniquely expressed as a product of prime numbers. The sequence of prime numbers begins with 2, 3, 5, 7, 11, 13, and so on, cataloged as sequence <https://oeis.org/A000040> in the Online Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences (OEIS). The property of being prime is intrinsic to the number itself, independent of the numeral system used to express it.

1.2 Terminological Clarification: Defining Primal and Compound Numbers

To ensure clear communication and avoid terminological ambiguities in this study, we present a clarification of the terms 'Primal Numbers' and 'Compound Numbers.' These concepts represent an expansion of conventional definitions, covering a broader spectrum of integers, including their negative counterparts and the number zero, aiming to enhance our discussion on the classification of integers. Below, we detail each term and its corresponding translation, establishing the lexicon used throughout this work.

In English:

Primal Number: Refers to an integer that extends the concept of traditional prime numbers to include their negative counterparts and the numbers 1 and -1.

Primal Numbers: The plural form of "Primal Number", encompassing the set of all numbers considered primal.

Primals: An informal abbreviation for "Primal Numbers", equivalent to how "Primes" refers to prime numbers.

Compound Number: A number defined within a broader set than traditional composite numbers, including both positive and negative integers, as well as the number zero.

Compound Numbers: The plural form of "Compound Number", referring to the set of all numbers that fall under the compound category.

Compounds: An informal abbreviation for "Compound Numbers", used similarly to "Composites" to refer to composite numbers.

Em português (Brasil):

Número Primal: Refere-se a um número inteiro que estende o conceito de números primos tradicionais para incluir seus equivalentes negativos e os números 1 e -1.

Números Primais: A forma plural de "Número Primal", abrangendo o conjunto de todos os números considerados primais.

Primais: Uma abreviação informal para "Números Primais", equivalente ao uso de "Primos" para se referir aos números primos.

Número Compósito: Um número definido dentro de um conjunto mais amplo que os números compostos tradicionais, incluindo tanto inteiros positivos quanto negativos, além do número zero.

Números Compósitos: A forma plural de "Número Compósito", referindo-se ao conjunto de todos os números que se enquadram na categoria compósito.

Compósitos: Uma abreviação informal para "Números Compósitos", usada de maneira semelhante a "Compostos" para se referir aos números compostos.

1.3 Diversity and Evolution of Definitions

The varied and evolving definitions of prime numbers across languages underscore the necessity for a revised perspective that accommodates a broader spectrum of integers. This discussion sets the stage for proposing 'Primal Numbers' and 'Compound Numbers' as categories that reflect a more inclusive understanding of integer classification, incorporating both negative integers and zero.

Different languages and sources present divergent definitions of prime numbers. For instance, on May 16, 2017, the English definition found at https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/prime_number stated: *“A prime number (or a prime) is a natural number greater than 1 that has no positive divisors other than 1 and itself. A natural number greater than 1 that is not a prime number is called a composite number.”*

However, on September 24, 2023, at the same link, the definition changed to: *“A prime number (or a prime) is a natural number greater than 1 that is not a product of two smaller natural numbers. A natural number greater than 1 that is not prime is called a composite number.”*

In Brazilian Portuguese, the definition of prime numbers stands out as markedly different, potentially leading to a distinct classification and understanding of primes. On May 16, 2017, the definition found at https://pt.wikipedia.org/wiki/número_primo outlined:

“A prime number is a number P whose set of non-invertible divisors is not empty, and all its elements are products of P by invertible integers. According to this definition, 0, 1 and -1 are not prime numbers.”

(“Número primo, é um número P cujo conjunto dos divisores não inversíveis não é vazio, e todos os seus elementos são produtos de P por números inteiros inversíveis. De acordo com esta definição, 0, 1 e -1 não são números primos.”).

On May 16, 2017, the Spanish definition of primes found at https://es.wikipedia.org/wiki/número_primo closely resembled a literal translation of the earlier English version. Additionally, it specified that composite numbers can be factored, and conventionally, the number 1 is neither classified as prime nor composite.

(“En matemáticas, un número primo es un número natural mayor que 1 que tiene únicamente dos divisores distintos: él mismo y el 1. Por el contrario, los números compuestos son los números naturales que tienen algún divisor natural aparte de sí mismos y del 1 y por lo tanto, pueden factorizarse. El número 1, por convenio, no se considera ni primo ni compuesto.”).

1.4 Primal Numbers

Primal numbers, as introduced for the purposes of our discussion, extend the concept of prime numbers by including both positive and negative integers that mirror the prime numbers and, uniquely, the number 1. Unlike the conventional definition of prime numbers, which exclusively encompasses positive integers greater than 1, primal numbers include the corresponding negative counterparts and the number 1, considering them as foundational elements in a broader numerical system. Thus, primal numbers consist of $\pm 1, \pm 2, \pm 3, \pm 5, \pm 7, \pm 11$, and so forth. This extended set embraces the idea that the divisibility and multiplicative properties that characterize prime numbers can be conceptually mirrored across zero to include negative integers and the historically contentious number 1. The inclusion of negative integers and 1 under the umbrella of primal numbers acknowledges a symmetrical perspective on the number line, wherein the prime structure and its significance are mirrored in the negative domain, alongside the unique inclusion of 1 as a primal entity.

In essence, while prime numbers <https://oeis.org/A000040> adhere to a strict and widely accepted mathematical definition focusing on positive integers greater than 1, primal numbers introduce a novel, expansive concept that includes both positive and negative integers of the prime sequence, alongside the number 1. This conceptual framework allows for an extended exploration of divisibility and multiplicative properties across the entire integer spectrum, acknowledging the foundational role of numbers traditionally excluded from the prime classification.

1.5 Definition of Compound Numbers

In the realm of mathematical discourse, the introduction of precise terminology is pivotal for the clear communication of concepts and theories. This document proposes the term "compound

numbers" to denote a comprehensive set of numbers that expands upon the traditional definition of composite numbers. Herein, we outline the definition and scope of "compound numbers" within an academic context.

Compound numbers are defined as the set of all integers that are not prime, encompassing not only positive composite numbers but also including the number zero (0) and negative integers that mirror the positive composite numbers in their divisibility properties. Specifically, this set includes:

1. Positive Composite Numbers: Integers greater than 1 that have more than two distinct positive divisors.

2. The Number Zero (0): Uniquely characterized by its infinite divisibility, zero is neither prime nor traditionally composite but is included in the set of compound numbers due to its fundamental role in arithmetic and algebra.

3. Negative Composite Numbers: Negative integers that are the additive inverses of the positive composite numbers, thereby sharing their divisibility characteristics.

1.6 Discussion on Divisor Pairs

Individual interpretations further diversify the spectrum of definitions. An interpretation put forth on October 19, 2020, defined prime numbers as outcomes derived from the multiplication of natural numbers, with a single factor of that product equating to 1. As expressed in a publication at https://easychair.org/publications/preprint_open/rSJd, I stated that *"prime numbers are all the numbers that result from only one product of natural numbers, with only one factor of that product being equal to number 1"*.

Individual interpretations of prime numbers further diversify the range of definitions. An analysis rooted in the concept of complementary pairs of divisors provides a solid foundation for distinguishing between 'Primal Numbers' and 'Compound Numbers,' highlighting the importance of revisiting traditional classifications.

Given these differences, exploring various definitions of prime numbers across languages and historical contexts becomes intriguing, akin to contrasting translations of Pythagoras' theorem.

Among the diverse definitions, a notable and straightforward explanation of a prime number is presented by Scott Aaronson in "The Prime Facts: From Euclid to AKS" © 2003 [1]: "A whole number with exactly two divisors."

In reflecting upon the definition offered by Scott Aaronson, 'A whole number with exactly two divisors,' it becomes evident that a critical specification is implied yet not explicitly stated: these two divisors are understood to be positive. This clarification is paramount, as both -11 and +11 indeed have four divisors when considering both positive and negative divisors, which deviates from the traditional criteria for primality. The unique case of -1, having exactly two divisors, -1 and +1, further illustrates the necessity of this specification. Thus, for the definition to align with the conventional understanding of prime numbers in number theory, it should be refined to: 'A whole number with exactly two positive divisors.' This adjustment ensures that the definition excludes negative integers and is consistent with the principle that prime numbers are

positive integers greater than 1, whose only divisors are 1 and themselves. This nuanced clarification underlines the importance of precision in mathematical definitions and supports the conventional classification of prime numbers, while acknowledging the special characteristics of certain integers like -1.

1.7 Objective Clarification

Building upon the historical and contemporary definitions of prime numbers, this study aims to introduce and justify the concepts of 'Primal Numbers' and 'Compound Numbers.' This initiative emerges from a detailed analysis of prime number sieves across the entire number line, recognizing the roles of negative integers, zero, and unity within mathematical frameworks. Our intention is to offer a new perspective for classifying integers that transcends the conventional prime-composite dichotomy."

With a deeper interpretation of prime number sieves, a revised definition emerges: "An integer number with only one pair of complementary positive divisors." According to this definition, integers with multiple pairs of complementary positive divisors are classified as composites, aligning with the foundational principle learned from the multiplication table **Error! Reference source not found.**

In extending the traditional concept of prime numbers to include both positive and negative integers under the term 'primal numbers,' it is crucial to consider the role of both positive and negative divisors while maintaining consistency with traditional definitions of primality. A primal number, by this expanded definition, is one that has exactly one pair of positive complementary divisors. For example, the primal number 7 has the divisors 1 and 7, constituting one pair of positive complementary divisors. Similarly, -7, while being a negative integer, mirrors this property in the negative domain and is thus considered a primal number because it corresponds to a unique set of positive divisors, 1 and 7, when considering its absolute value.

This interpretation allows for the inclusion of -1 as a primal number, unique in having itself and 1 as its only two divisors, though it diverges from traditional classifications by considering the divisors of -1 to be both -1 and 1, fitting within our expanded definition. In this framework, primal numbers include both their positive and negative counterparts, acknowledging the symmetry on the number line and the foundational role of these integers in a broader numerical system.

The distinction becomes particularly important when discussing the divisibility and multiplicative properties that characterize primal numbers. By this expanded understanding, numbers like 7 and -7 are seen as having a singular pair of positive complementary divisors, aligning them with the conceptual framework of primal numbers. This sieve-based perspective accommodates both positive and negative integers, enhancing our exploration of number theory by including negative integers as primal numbers due to their similar divisibility properties to their positive counterparts.

Conversely, the classification of the number 0 demands a nuanced understanding. While 0 is considered a compound number in our framework, this is not due to a lack of positive divisors.

In fact, every non-zero integer, positive or negative, can be seen as a divisor of 0 when paired with 0 itself (since any number multiplied by 0 yields 0). This unique property of 0, being divisible by every non-zero integer, distinguishes it from primal numbers, which are defined by having exactly one pair of positive complementary divisors. Thus, the infinite divisibility of 0 - its ability to be divided by any non-zero integer without remainder - places it within the category of compound numbers. This special consideration for 0 enriches the mathematical landscape by highlighting its unique role in divisibility and classification, differentiating it from both primal and traditional prime numbers.

1.8 Justification for the Term "Compound Numbers"

The term "compound" is chosen for its connotations of combining multiple elements to form a whole, reflecting the diverse nature of the included integers. Unlike the term "composite numbers," which strictly refers to positive integers greater than one that are not prime, "compound numbers" offers a broader classification that acknowledges the arithmetic symmetry between positive and negative integers and the unique mathematical status of zero.

1.9 Importance and Applications

The concept of "compound numbers" originates from a recognized gap within mathematical terminology, specifically identified through the exploration of prime number sieves and prime sequences. This term effectively encapsulates integers that have traditionally been omitted from the composite numbers category due to their distinctive signs or unique properties, such as zero. Importantly, the harmonization of prime sieves and prime sequences necessitates the inclusion of negative primes and the numbers 1 and -1, underscoring the broad spectrum of integers within number theory. By introducing "compound numbers," we address these exclusions, enhancing the structure of mathematical classification and supporting a more inclusive analysis of integer properties and relationships.

1.10 Reflection on the Comprehensive Classification

The exploration of 'Primal Numbers' and 'Compound Numbers' suggests subtle yet meaningful enhancements to the classification of integers, inspired by an in-depth look at prime number sieves. This nuanced approach doesn't seek to overturn established principles such as the [Fundamental Theorem of Arithmetic](#) but instead invites us to reflect on enriching our mathematical lexicon and theoretical frameworks. By considering the inclusion of broader definitions, we might uncover new insights into number theory that embrace the entire spectrum of integers, potentially revealing unexplored connections within mathematics.

2 The Finitude of Integers and the Nature of Infinity

The current understanding of mathematics, in many respects, resembles the state of Newtonian physics before Einstein's revelations. Just as Einstein transformed physics with his theory of relativity, we still have much to learn about the nuances surrounding the concept of infinity and division by zero in mathematics.

2.1 Reflections on Finitude and Infinity

Each integer is characterized by a unit digit ranging from 0 to 9, and its fractional part, if any, must consist solely of 0s or 9s. This allows us to categorize each integer as either even or odd. On the other hand, infinity represents an arbitrarily extensive, undefinable magnitude without clear limits. Unlike integers, infinity cannot be classified as even or odd, lacks an identifiable unit digit, and does not have a defined fractional part. For these reasons, infinity is generally excluded from the category of numbers. These observations highlight our inability to fully comprehend infinity and its variations.

Thus, integers are finite entities, distinct from infinity. However, the infinite collection of integers, despite being composed of finite entities, is not an integer itself. This contradiction arises from our acceptance of the infinite nature of integers while denying that infinity is a number. The debate intensifies when we claim that the quantity of integers is infinite, though infinity itself is not classified as a number.

2.2 Highly Composite Numbers (HCN) and the Singularity of Zero

Highly Composite Numbers (HCN) <https://oeis.org/A002182>, recognized for their record number of positive divisors, introduce an important perspective to this discussion. Considering that zero appears in all prime number sieves and represents a finite integer, we propose that it be viewed as the only finite integer with an infinite number of positive divisors. Symbolically, zero acts as a starting point on the journey towards infinity, being the supreme HCN among all numbers. Interestingly, as we move towards positive or negative infinity, we encounter numbers with the fewest positive divisors: ± 1 .

2.3 Relationship between Primes and HCNs

Every integer greater than 1, regardless of its magnitude, is classified as either prime or composite, a distinction that also leads us to the understanding of HCNs. Each HCN sets new records in terms of divisor count, while each prime number demonstrates perpetual constancy of two distinct positive divisors. This dynamic between prime numbers and HCNs extends the numerical line to positive infinity, underscoring the finitude of divisors for positive or negative integers.

Integers, both positive and negative, are defined by a finite number of divisors, differentiating them from the concept of infinity. When contemplating prime number sieves, we observe that each number is defined by its relationship with the unit divisor, raising profound questions about the nature of infinity in mathematics.

3 The Parabolic Sieve of Primes

In the study "The Hyperbolic Sieve of Prime Numbers" [8], the triangular and square multiplication tables reveal no distinction between the primality of number 1 and all other primes. Consider, for example, "A Visual Sieve for Prime Numbers" published on February 14, 1999, by Yuri Matiyasevich and Boris Stechkin, accessible online at <https://logic.pdmi.ras.ru/~yumat/personaljournal/sieve/sieve.html>. See the reproduction below:

C002800 Figure 1 Reproduction of the figure used by Matiyasevich, Yuri and Stechkin, Boris. (1999) "A visual Sieve for Prime Numbers", available online at <https://logic.pdmi.ras.ru/~yumat/personaljournal/sieve/sieve.gif>.

Do you perceive any difference in results between prime numbers with two distinct positive divisors <https://oeis.org/A000040> from the number 1? The answer: there is no difference.

3.1 Understanding the Role of Number 1

It might be contended that the number 1 is not considered primal because, just as the number 2 connects with another 2 covering 4 on the numerical line, or the number 3 connects with another 3 covering 9, similarly, the number 1 connects with another 1 covering 1 on the numerical line. However, within this logic, it is crucial to recognize that the number 1 connects with all other integers, spanning the entirety of the numerical line, akin to all positive integers intersecting the line at their multiples.

The number 1 connects with itself and all other integers to form what we term the 'trivial pair of complementary divisors.' Thus, the connection of the number 1 with any other integer implies that all integers are multiples of the primal number 1, including itself. The divisor 1 does not discern whether a number larger than itself is primal or compound; indeed, all integers are multiples of it.

If this sieve were to include connections of the number 1 in the same manner as other integers, it would result in all integers on the numerical line having an additional line referencing the number 1. Consequently, instead of compounds requiring at least one covering line, including the lines from number 1, compounds would necessitate at least two lines. Notably, the number of lines intersecting number 1 would never be less than or greater than the number of lines associated with other primal numbers.

3.2 Deconstructing the Connection Patterns

As previously stated, the definition that "number 1 is not the product of two smaller natural numbers" prompts a reevaluation of the prime numbers sieve and the [Fundamental Theorem of Arithmetic](#). Distinctly, the exclusion of number 1 from prime classification is a convention established by us.

In the referenced figure, it's observed that no line connects point 1 to any other points or integers. Thus, number 1 on the number line remains uncovered by lines from preceding positive integers, on par with subsequent prime numbers such as 2, 3, 5, 7, 11, 13, and beyond. Only composite numbers are intersected by lines formed by integers smaller than themselves.

Taking number 4 as an example, intersected by the line connecting two 2s (since $2 \times 2 = 4$), if we were to draw all lines from the two 1s over the parabola, it would reveal that number 4 on the number line is also covered by these two lines, from 1 to 4, of the parabola. This is because 4 equals 1×4 and also 4×1 . Therefore, it can be concluded that number 4 possesses three positive distinct divisors: $\{1, 2, 4\}$. Alternatively, number 4 also has two pairs of complementary positive divisors: $(1;4)$ and $(2;2)$, a principle that extends to any integer.

3.3 Redefining the Concept of Primal Integers: The Unique Positions of 1 and -1, and Their Implications

As we navigate through the complex terrain of mathematics, the distinction between primal and compound integers requires a nuanced understanding, particularly when considering the unique positions of 1 and -1. These integers defy conventional classifications, prompting a reevaluation of their roles within the number system.

1 and -1 are foundational to the integer spectrum, possessing unique properties that challenge traditional mathematical norms. The universal divisibility of 1, alongside -1's ability to invert the sign of any integer it multiplies, positions them as primal integers. This designation transcends the usual prime-composite dichotomy, inviting a broader classification that acknowledges their fundamental roles.

When analyzing the multiplication of two factors resulting in an integer not equal to ± 1 , it becomes evident that neither 1 nor -1 should be considered as a factor in the context of primal numbers. This principle extends to -1 as well, underlining the intrinsic presence of 1 as a factor or divisor across all integers. However, this ubiquity does not lend itself to distinguishing or categorizing integers, rendering 1 and -1 as non-factors in any product other than themselves. This realization foregrounds the importance of identifying a pair of complementary divisors, a concept pivotal to differentiating primal numbers from compounds.

Employing primal number sieves to discern compound numbers inherently avoids the use of divisor 1, sidestepping the trivial pair of complementary divisors that do not differentiate primal from compound numbers. This methodology highlights that every integer encapsulates a trivial pair of complementary divisors, thereby necessitating a more discerning approach to classification.

This sieve method brings to light the following conclusions:

- Every primal number is characterized by a trivial pair of complementary divisors identical to the central pair of complementary divisors.
- Conversely, every compound number features a trivial pair of complementary divisors distinct from the central pair of complementary divisors.

Such insights affirm that there is no distinguishing characteristic between the number 1 and other primal numbers, establishing 1 as the inaugural primal number among all positive integers. This approach unambiguously qualifies the number 1 as a primal number, reinforcing the need for a redefined perspective on primal integers that includes both 1 and -1 due to their intrinsic mathematical significance.

3.4 Primal Numbers in Negative Integers

Could a mirrored parabolic sieve that reflects the negative integers on the number line be conceivable? There's nothing that precludes such an endeavor. Extending this perspective, we discover that numbers like -1, -2, -3, -5, -7, -11, -13, and so on, exhibit primality akin to their positive counterparts.

The sieve of primal numbers unequivocally demonstrates that negative primal numbers share identical characteristics with positive primal numbers, each possessing just one pair of complementary positive divisors. This insight is derived from the inherent symmetry along the number line, which aligns with a SUB-type of polynomial sequence.

3.5 Defining Number 0 as Compound

The integer zero stands alongside positive and negative integers within the sieve's framework. It's imperative to forge connections between zero and all integers arrayed along both flanks of the parabolic sieve. The exclusion of zero's linkage appears arbitrary—why should such a fundamental integer be disregarded?

The absence of number 0, next to the positions of number 1 in the sieve, was simply a choice by the authors, not a necessity. There's no impediment to amending these oversights, akin to introducing red coloration to highlight number 1 among the blue-colored integers. As previously demonstrated, number 1 aligns with other primal numbers.

From this sieve, we deduce that number 0 shares the compound nature with both positive and negative compound numbers from the sequence <https://oeis.org/A002808>. The distinction lies in zero being a compound number with an infinite number of positive divisors, unlike other compound integers in the sequence, which have a finite count of positive divisors.

Alternatively, it might be construed that zero has an infinite number of pairs of complementary divisors, while other compound numbers have a finite count greater than one of such pairs. Essentially, all compound numbers, beyond the trivial pair of complementary divisors, possess a finite number of these pairs.

4 The Sieve of Primes based on Leonhard Euler's Sigma Function

In 1751, Leonhard Euler proposed, *"Having so established this sign S to indicate the sum of the divisors of the number in front of which it is placed, it is clear that, if p indicates a prime number, the value of S_p will be $1 + p$, except for the case where $p = 1$, because then we have $S_1 = 1$, and not $S_1 = 1 + 1$. From this we see that we must exclude unity from the sequence of prime numbers, so that unity, being the start of whole numbers, is neither prime nor composite."* This note is within the sequence <https://oeis.org/A008578>.

4.1 Redefining Unique Properties of Primal Numbers and Their Classifications

Considering the number 1 as primal, it stands out as the only positive primal number that is also a square, expressed in the form $x(x \pm 0)$ (see <https://oeis.org/A000290>). Uniquely, it is the sole square number also considered primal. Since square numbers cannot be negative, -1

represents the negative counterpart of this unique square primal number. Similarly, -4 serves as the negative square of the primal number 2, and so on.

Discussing the primal number 2, akin to number 1, it is the only primal number that exhibits an oblong shape, formulated as $x(x \pm 1)$ (see <https://oeis.org/A002378>), and is the exclusive oblong number deemed primal.

Number 3 is acknowledged as the unique positive primal number that embodies a (square minus 1) figure, articulated as $x(x \pm 2)$ (see <https://oeis.org/A005563>), and is the sole (square minus 1) number identified as primal. This pattern extends to every primal number, where each aligns with an exclusive quadratic Composite Generator (CG) in the form of $x(x \pm (\text{primal} - 1))$ — the designated primal being the singular primal number within an infinite sequence of compound numbers.

This perspective redefines our understanding of primal and compound numbers, following the proposed expansion of traditional classifications to encompass the specific nuances of numbers like 1 and -1 , while also addressing the unique position of the number 0 within the context of compound numbers.

4.2 4.2 Defining Primality by Positive Divisor Count

While compound numbers possess more than two positive divisors, square numbers have an odd number of positive divisors. The parity of positive divisors in integers, however, does not define their primality; it is the count of positive divisors that distinguishes their primality. Euler's postulate emphasizes that all primal numbers greater than 1 have the sum of their positive divisors equal to $(P+1)$, with the sole exception of number 1, which has the sum of its positive divisors equal to 1, underlining two key assertions:

- All primal numbers possess 1 or 2 positive divisors; number 1 has a single positive divisor, belonging to the class of square numbers, while any other primal number exhibits two positive divisors.
- All compounds, except 0, exhibit a finite number of positive divisors greater than 2, while the compound number 0 possesses an infinite number of positive divisors. Despite the sum of its positive divisors being infinite, it is deemed a compound number due to its unique position of having an infinite count of positive divisors.

These insights serve not only to differentiate between primal and compound numbers based on divisor counts but also emphasize the unique positions of numbers 1 and 0 within these classifications."

4.3 Defining Primality by Divisor Count

While composite numbers possess more than two positive divisors, square numbers possess an odd number of divisors. However, the parity of divisors in integers does not define their primality; rather, it is the count of divisors that distinguishes their primality.

Euler's postulate, emphasizing that all prime numbers greater than 1 have the sum of their divisors equal to $(P + 1)$, and solely number 1 has the sum of its divisors equal to 1, underlines two key assertions:

- All prime numbers possess 1 or 2 divisors; number 1 has 1 divisor, belonging to the class of square numbers, while any other prime number exhibits an even number of divisors.
- All composites, except 0, exhibit a finite number of divisors greater than 2, whereas composite number 0 possesses an infinite number of divisors, albeit the sum of its positive divisors being infinite, it is deemed a composite number.

4.4 Evaluating Euler's Sigma Function for Primality Detection

The sum of all divisors for any integer would ostensibly result in zero due to the pairing of each positive divisor with its negative counterpart. However, when using Euler's Sigma function ($\text{Sigma}(n)$), which aggregates only the positive divisors of an integer (refer to <https://oeis.org/A000203> for more information), we adopt a nuanced approach to identify primality:

- For primal numbers: $\text{Sigma}(n)$ should be less than or equal to $(1 + n)$. This criterion fits primal numbers since, by definition, they possess a minimal set of divisors.
- For compound numbers: $\text{Sigma}(n)$ is greater than $(1 + n)$. This is because compound numbers have additional divisors beyond the trivial pair, thereby increasing the sum of their divisors.

Trivial divisors include 1 and the integer itself for any number n . Compound numbers are distinguished by their complementary pair of trivial divisors along with one or more additional divisors, leading to a total sum of divisors that surpasses that of trivial divisors alone.

Primal numbers, in contrast, are defined by a singular pair of complementary positive divisors. For primal numbers greater than 1, the sum of their positive trivial divisors coincides with the total sum of all their positive divisors.

The number 1 is exceptional, featuring a unique pair of identical positive trivial divisors, positioning it as a square number—the only integer with precisely one positive divisor. This singular property establishes that $\text{Sigma}(1)$ is less than $(1 + 1)$, hence aligning it more closely with the characteristics of primal numbers in terms of divisor count.

5 Sieve Based on A006005

In the discourse surrounding the classification of the number 1 as an odd positive primal number, reference to the sequence documented at <https://oeis.org/A006005> and insights derived from Gerry Martens' examination of the prime sieve provide substantial grounds for discussion and reinterpretation.

The mentioned sequence in the Online Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences (OEIS) enumerates odd positive primal numbers, within which the number 1 often finds itself in a contentious position regarding its primal status. Traditional mathematical conventions delineate prime numbers as those exceeding 1 that are indivisible by any positive integers aside from 1 and themselves, a criterion from which the number 1 notably deviates due to its unique properties.

Gerry Martens' analytical commentary on the prime sieve notably considers the mathematical expression $\cos\left(\frac{(k-1)\pi}{k}\right)$ and its negativity as indicative of odd k numbers being primal. Specifically, for $k = 1$, this expression simplifies to $\cos(0! * \pi) = \cos(\pi)$, yielding a negative outcome, thereby satisfying the sieve's criteria for primal identification.

This perspective, underscored by the sieve's methodology that classifies odd positive primal numbers based on the condition $\cos\left(\frac{(k-1)\pi}{k}\right) < 0$, intriguingly suggests the inclusion of the number 1 within the odd positive primal numbers category according to the unique evaluation framework provided by this sieve method.

6 Sieve Insights from A008578 and Primorial Numbers in A002110

6.1 Exploring the Sieve through A008578

The sequence cataloged at <https://oeis.org/A008578> introduces a range of insightful sieves that enhance our comprehension of primal number delineation, featuring contributions such as:

- Numbers k for which the largest divisor less than or equal to $\sqrt{k}$ is 1, a sieve proposed by Omar E. Pol on July 5, 2009, which emphasizes a unique approach to identifying primal numbers.
- Instances where record values of "Least highly composite number divisible by n " are observed, as identified by Reinhard Zumkeller on June 21, 2010. This method utilizes $A086332(n) = A022404(a(n))$ to spotlight specific highly composite numbers.
- Positive integers devoid of divisors besides 1 and themselves, reverting to an older definition of prime numbers as outlined by Omar E. Pol on August 10, 2012.

Intriguingly, these varied interpretations underscore a nuanced understanding of primal numbers without necessarily disputing the classification of the number 1 as a prime.

6.2 A002110 and the Primorial Concept

The framing of the number 1 as a primal number aligns seamlessly with its inclusion in the sequence documented at <https://oeis.org/A002110>, known for listing primorial numbers. The inclusion of 1 within this sequence not only adheres to but also underscores the logical extension of primal numbers, affirming its foundational role within the primorial numbers framework and reinforcing its intrinsic value in the realm of number theory.

7 Revisiting the Concept of the "Oddest" Primal Number: Reflections on Primal 2 and the Inclusion of Negative Primals

In the mathematical discourse surrounding primal numbers, the characterization of primal 2 as the "oddest" among them due to its evenness has periodically surfaced in debates. Labeling primal 2 as such may deviate from the core understanding of primal numbers. "Even" and "odd," terms established to differentiate multiples from non-multiples of 2, stem from human intellect, yet the distinction between primal and compound numbers roots deeply in mathematical tradition.

7.1 The Unique Status of Primal 2 and the Consideration of Primal -1

Primal 2 uniquely stands as the sole even positive primal number, distinguished as the only non-negative even integer classified as primal. This distinction sets it apart from all other positive primal numbers for not having antecedent factors with two distinct positive divisors. The discussion of primal -1 brings to light the symmetry in primal properties across the number line, recognizing 1 and -1 as unique for having only one positive divisor—a characteristic not shared by other primal numbers. While identifying primal 2 as the "oddest" might misrepresent primal numbers' nuanced essence, recognizing the individual uniqueness of each primal number, including -1, accentuates their distinctiveness, whether positive or negative.

7.2 Variations Among Primal Numbers, Including Negative Primals

The distinctiveness of primal numbers becomes apparent with primal 3, which stands out as peculiar. Being the only primal divisible by 3, it marks the earliest non-negative multiple of 3 deemed primal, devoid of preceding factors with two distinct positive divisors. This quality allows primal 3 to categorize integers into "multiples of 3" and "non-multiples of 3." Likewise, primal 5 echoes this uniqueness as the only primal multiple of 5, akin to primal 3's distinction. These observations extend to negative primals like -3 and -5, sharing primality with their positive counterparts and highlighting primal numbers' symmetrical attributes across the number line.

7.3 Defining and Classifying Primal Numbers

Primal numbers, emanating from a singular multiplication of two positive factors, exhibit only one set of complementary positive divisors. In contrast, compound numbers originate from varied factorizations, featuring more than one set of complementary positive divisors. Efforts to categorize primal numbers through methods like Legendre's conjecture or modular arithmetic (mod 4) illustrate diverse primal attributes. Nonetheless, such methodologies do not ascribe greater oddness to any particular primal. These endeavors underscore that primal numbers maintain an equal standing in their uniqueness, devoid of an "oddness" hierarchy.

This comprehensive reflection on primal 2 and the encompassing discussion of primal and compound numbers strive to expand the understanding of mathematical principles that govern

the realm of integers, acknowledging the intricacies and individuality present within the spectrum of primal numbers.

8 Is There an Oddest Prime Number?

In the exploration of mathematical unconventionalities, the discourse surrounding the peculiarities of primal numbers presents an intriguing dialogue. Within this sphere, the distinction of the number 1 as a primal number, alongside its counterpart -1, introduces a nuanced debate on their singularity. Traditionally, the delineation of primal numbers has adhered to a criterion that excludes 1 from the primal category, primarily due to its possession of a single positive divisor—namely, itself. This convention, however, is challenged by a broader perspective that seeks to redefine the essence of primality, extending the concept to encapsulate both 1 and -1 in their respective domains.

1, as the only positive primal number with a singular positive divisor, diverges from the normative attributes ascribed to primal numbers, which are typically characterized by exactly two distinct positive divisors. This anomaly positions 1 as the "oddest" among positive primal numbers, given its unique divisor property that does not parallel any other number within the positive primal spectrum.

Conversely, -1 emerges as the "oddest" among negative primal numbers, mirroring the distinctive divisor attribute of 1 within the negative realm. The inclusion of -1 underscores a symmetrical aspect of primal numbers, acknowledging the consistency of primal properties across the number line, thereby amplifying the dialogue on the uniqueness of primal numbers.

This reevaluation invites a deeper consideration of the "oddness" inherent to primal numbers, accentuating the peculiarities of 1 and -1 as pivotal examples that challenge traditional mathematical conventions. It highlights the necessity of embracing an expanded classification framework that not only acknowledges the unique positions of 1 and -1 but also enriches the understanding of primal numbers as a whole.

The concept of "oddness" in this context transcends mere numerical properties, venturing into the realm of mathematical anomalies where 1 and -1 stand as testaments to the complexity and depth of primal numbers. Their distinctiveness reaffirms the notion that each primal number, whether positive or negative, possesses its own "oddest" feature, derived from its unique divisibility traits and contributing to the rich tapestry of mathematical exploration.

Thus, in the realm of primal numbers, the question of whether there is an "oddest" primal number leads to a reflective acknowledgment of 1 and -1 as embodying the extremes of primal "oddness," a testament to the multifaceted nature of mathematical inquiry.

9 Is There an Oddest Composite Number?

In the contemplation of mathematical peculiarities, the query regarding the existence of an "oddest" compound number warrants a nuanced exploration, especially in light of discussions surrounding primal numbers. This inquiry is particularly compelling when considering the broad spectrum of integers, both positive and negative, within the classification of compound numbers.

Traditionally, compound numbers are defined by their factorization properties, distinguishable from primal numbers by having more than two distinct positive divisors. This definition inherently accommodates an infinite range of possibilities, given the nature of factorization and the diversity of compound numbers it produces. However, when delving into the attributes of compound numbers, a distinctive consideration arises with the integer zero (0).

Zero, unique in its mathematical properties, stands out as a singular entity within the compound classification. It is the only integer with an infinite number of divisors, a characteristic that starkly contrasts with the finite divisor count observed in other compound numbers. This infinite divisibility of zero not only underscores its uniqueness but also prompts a reevaluation of what constitutes the "oddest" within the compound category.

Expanding the perspective to encompass negative integers, the concept of "oddness" becomes even more profound. Negative compound numbers, mirroring their positive counterparts in terms of factorization, contribute to the rich complexity of the compound classification. Yet, even among these, zero maintains its unparalleled position due to its aforementioned infinite divisibility.

Thus, when considering the vast landscape of compound numbers, both positive and negative, the designation of zero as the "oddest" compound number emerges as a compelling argument. Its singular nature, characterized by an unlimited divisor capacity, positions it as an outlier, challenging conventional notions of factorization and divisibility.

This exploration into the "oddest" compound number, underscored by the unique status of zero, enriches the discourse on mathematical classifications. It illuminates the intricate balance between the finite and infinite, the positive and negative, thereby advancing our understanding of the fundamental nature of numbers. In this context, zero's distinction as the "oddest" compound number reflects its arithmetic properties.

10 Exploring Primals and Compounds in the Multiplication Table Framework

Delving into the unique characteristics of primal and compound numbers through the lens of their manifestations in multiplication table equations, specifically in the form of $x = y(y + b)$, unveils a nuanced understanding of their distinctions. For an elaborate exploration, one might refer to the discussion "Understanding A056737 and the quadratic sequences: not so 'quibbles'" available at <https://www.mersenneforum.org/showpost.php?p=597461&postcount=14>, where x and y are considered as non-negative integers.

Number 1, emerging as the "oddest primal number" or the "first positive primal number," is uniquely present in the sequence of square numbers $x = y(y + 0)$ (<https://oeis.org/A000290>), and conspicuously absent from any other sequence modeled as $x = y(y + b)$.

The number 2, termed the "second positive primal number," features within the oblong numbers sequence $x = y(y + 1)$ (<https://oeis.org/A002378>), making no appearances in any prior sequence formatted as $x = y(y + b)$ for $0 \leq b < 1$.

Further along, number 3, labeled as the "third positive primal number," surfaces within the sequence $x = y(y + 2)$ (square minus 1 numbers, <https://oeis.org/A005563>), exclusive to any antecedent sequence structured as $x = y(y + b)$ for $0 \leq b < 2$.

Conversely, number 4 is acknowledged as a compound number, given its presence in the sequence $x = y(y + 3)$ (oblong minus 2 numbers, <https://oeis.org/A028552>) and its earlier appearance in the sequence of squares $x = y(y + 0)$ (<https://oeis.org/A000290>).

In contrast, number 5 is recognized as a primal number, as it emerges in the sequence $x = y(y + 4)$ (square minus 4 numbers, <https://oeis.org/A028347>) without manifesting in any preceding sequence shaped as $x = y(y + b)$ for $0 \leq b < 4$.

Meanwhile, number 6 is classified as a compound number due to its presence in the sequence $x = y(y + 5)$ (oblong minus 6 numbers, <https://oeis.org/A028557>) and its previous inclusion in the sequence of oblongs $x = y(y + 1)$ (<https://oeis.org/A002378>).

Additionally, number 7 is deemed a primal number for appearing in the sequence $x = y(y + 6)$ (square minus 9 numbers, <https://oeis.org/A028560>) and not featuring in any prior sequence defined as $x = y(y + b)$ for $0 \leq b < 6$.

This pattern perpetuates infinitely, with each number finding its place within a specific mathematical narrative.

Notably, number 0, manifesting across all previously mentioned sequences, is distinguished as "the oddest compound number," reinforcing the concept of 0 as a mathematical outlier with unique properties distinct from other numbers in the context of primal and compound classification.

11 Insights into Primals ± 1 and the Composite 0

In the landscape of integers:

- Every integer is marked by a finite value, distinctly separating it from concepts like infinity.
- Each integer, aside from 0, boasts a finite set of distinct divisors, illustrating the diverse nature of divisibility across the spectrum of numbers.

However, 0 emerges as an outlier due to its infinite divisibility, carving out a unique niche for itself in number theory.

Reflecting on the primal numbers ± 1 , their uniqueness is encapsulated in:

- Primal +1 being a universal divisor, maintaining the integrity of any integer it divides. This feature places +1 in a unique category within the primal numbers.
- In contrast, primal -1 uniquely transforms the sign of any integer it divides, reflecting the balanced properties of primal numbers on both sides of the numerical line.

Meanwhile, 0's distinctive role is highlighted by:

- Its divisibility by primal numbers ± 1 in any quantity, invariably resulting in 0. This trait underlines 0's role as a neutral entity within the numerical spectrum.
- 0's exclusivity as a composite that does not act as a divisor for any other integer, emphasizing its unique position among numbers. This peculiarity of 0 prompts further inquiry into its self-divisibility and broader implications in mathematical theories.

These considerations of the primal numbers ± 1 and the composite 0 enrich our understanding of their roles within mathematical discourse.

12 Definition and Classification of Primal Numbers

A primal number is characterized by having a unique pair of complementary positive divisors, distinguishing it within the spectrum of integers. It emerges as the only classification of numbers for which the central pair of complementary divisors aligns with the trivial pair: $(d_{c1}; d_{c2}) = (d_{t1}; d_{t2})$. It is imperative to emphasize that changing the order or sign of the divisors within this pair does not yield a distinct set, maintaining the uniqueness of the primal classification.

This broad definition embraces both positive and negative primal integers, adhering to the principle that a primal number contains no more than two distinct positive divisors. This approach to integer division, focusing exclusively on positive divisors, facilitates a detailed classification.

For integers featuring exactly one positive divisor, we identify the unique primal numbers +1 and -1. These numbers are distinguished as the only members within their category, embodying the concept of primal numbers without any preceding integers with similar divisibility properties.

If an integer is characterized by exactly two distinct positive divisors, it is acknowledged as a primal number greater than 1 or less than -1. This category defines the realm of primal numbers, exemplified by the DES-type sequence $\pm\{1,2,3,5,7,11,13,17,19,\dots\}$, which can be found at [±\(https://oeis.org/A008578\)](https://oeis.org/A008578). This group includes:

- All primal numbers, positive and negative alike, as symbolized by $\pm$ (<https://oeis.org/A000040>), which display exactly two distinct positive divisors.
- The unique numbers ± 1 , often considered the "oddest primal numbers", each defined by having a singular positive divisor.

This comprehensive definition and classification encapsulate the essence of primal numbers across the spectrum of positive and negative integers.

13 The Definition and Classification of Compound Numbers

A compound number is defined as any integer that displays more than one pair of complementary positive divisors. In the realm of integers, compound numbers are uniquely identified by their central pair of complementary divisors being different from the trivial pair: $(d_{c1}; d_{c2}) \neq (d_{t1}; d_{t2})$. The designation of a number as compound hinges on the criterion that its central pair of complementary divisors does not replicate the trivial pair.

The category of compound numbers, as denoted by $\pm\{0,4,6,8,9,10,12,14,15,16,18,20,21,\dots\}$, includes all integers that have more than two distinct positive divisors. This grouping comprises:

- All positive and negative compound numbers listed within $\pm(\text{https://oeis.org/A002808})$, which are characterized by having a finite number greater than two of distinct positive divisors.
- The number 0 is highlighted as the "oddest compound number," distinguished by being the only integer with an infinite count of distinct positive divisors.

Importantly, compound numbers are differentiated by their possession of multiple pairs of complementary divisors, which distinguishes them from other integers based on their unique divisibility properties.

14 Conclusion

An isomorphism permeates all sieves for primal numbers, leading to a unified conclusion. Adhering strictly to the information delineated by any sieve for primal numbers unequivocally reveals fundamental facts:

- Both positive and negative integers are deemed primals.
- Both positive and negative integers are classified as compounds.
- The number 1 qualifies as a primal number.
- Similarly, the number -1 stands as a primal number.
- In contrast, the number 0 is identified as a compound number.
- All integers find their classification within either the primal or compound number categories.
- No other integer classes exist beyond these distinctions.

This universal truth remains consistent across all iterations of primal number sieves, unifying their findings and affirming the existence of only two fundamental classes of integers: primals and compounds.

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